

PROPAGANDA AND PROPAGATION OF GOU PRODUCTS AMONG HAVYAKAS: A STUDY RELATED TO MANGALURU REGION

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Abstract:

Indian cow is a sacred animal. We think of getting only milk and manure from Gou. Other than milk, cow urine and cow dung of Gou are also useful. These are converted into Gou products, which help everyone to improve and maintain good health and to keep eco- socio environment. Gou products are prepared out of different breeds of Desi cow called Gou. Use of gou products are popularized by havyaka families. With due respect to its Math, Havyaka members' popularized gou products to other communities also.

Key Words: Maa Gou, Desi Gou, Environment Friendly & Math

Introduction:

Earlier every family had Desi cow called Gou at their lively hood. They used it for milk, cow dung, manure and for ploughing their paddy and agricultural field. Now it is very rare to see such families. Shree Shree Raghaveshwara Bharathi Swamiji of Shree Ramachandrapura Math has been showing his love towards Gou Matha is remarkable. In his words - "The farmers are not aware of the significance and usefulness of the cow. They do not know that they can earn more money from the cows which do not give milk than the cows that give milk. Due to this ignorance, they sell the non-milk giving cows to butchers." There is a slogan in Kamadugha of Math, "cow based economy is dependent on cow dung and urine, not only milk". Desi Gou, both cow and bullock can be used not only to meet our traditional needs, its urine and cow dung can also be used as medicine and its products are environment friendly. So any products prepared out of milk, urine and dung of Gou is gavya products which is useful for agriculture, horticulture, Pharmaceuticals, in turn helps human beings. 'Maa Gou' is one of the concerns which manufacture and supplies products by using its own supply chain. These Gou products are used by havyaka families which are rarely known to others.

Objectives of the Study:

The main aim is to make known about the gou products and its use among the people. However there are certain specific objectives. They are,

- ✓ To identify the number of family who know the use of gou products.
- ✓ To examine the interest among the havyakas in gou products.
- ✓ To study the utility of the gavya products
- ✓ To encourage all havyakas to propogate and propogandize the gou products to others.

Need and Significance of Study:

Every human being must be aware of their health. Things with zero chemical are very rare now. Gou products are produced under indigenouse technology and are non chemical products. There is a need to know the use of gou products all over the country. In this point of view at an initial stage, a study is made among the havyaka community which is prominently participating for the sustainability and growth of Desi cows through using gou products. There are nearly 850 havyaka families in Mangaluru Region. Among them, a survey of a sample of 100 havyaka families is undertaken.

Limitation:

A primary study was made among the Havyaka community of Mangaluru Region. Opinions of 100 havyaka families of Mangaluru Region were considered. Analysis was made based on the opinion given by the respondents. There is a scope for further study in this area.

Methodology:

The study makes use of both primary and secondary data for its analysis. Major analysis is based on the primary data. Primary data is collected through interview method with the use of questionnaire. Data is also collected from the website and books. One hundred samples have selected at random among the havyaka families in the Mangaluru Region.

Analysis:

Users of Gou Products: In a survey, 73 families were used gou products and liked the products very much. Study showed that majority of havyaka families came to know about the products in recent years. 23 havyaka families has been using it for long time. 27 families were not used it so far. But among the unused, many do not

know about the availability of such products. Non availability at the destination of 7 families made them not to use it now.

Table 1: Use of Gou products- Duration	No. of Havyaka Families
Less than 1 year	2
1-5 years	41
6-10 years	19
Above 11 years	4
Some years back used& not using it now	7
Total users	73
Source: Field Survey in Mangaluru Region	

Key Factors for the Use of Gou Products: Among 73 user respondents, many gave multiple answers for the use of gou products. As showed in table-2, majority of the respondents have been giving more importance on health and showed their love towards Gou. 32 families take this product as medicine. Instead of using other medicine, they felt that gou products have good medicinal values and no side effects. Likewise, 32 families treated it as environment friendly. Due to these factors majority of respondents used these gou products.

Table 2: Factors for the use of Gou products	No. of Families
To protect the Gou(Desi cows)	52
Positive effect on health	56
As a medicine	32
Environment friendly	32
Source: Field Survey in Mangaluru Region	

Introducer for the Use of Gou Products: Maa Gou Products Pvt. Ltd. is the concern which manufactures and markets many varieties of gavya products. It has its own supply chain. These gou products are being popularly used by havyaka families. Among the introducers, as showed in table-3, credit of popularizing this product goes to Shree Ramachandrapura Math. 43 families were inspired to use these products by their beloved Math. 15 respondents have used it due to Havyaka Sabha programmes. Havyaka friends, Gou product vendors, Maa Gou Concern, Havyaka Mandala and Relatives also introduced these gou products to a few of havyaka families. It is to be noted that no Havyaka families were inspired by Medias. In fact, these gou products are not advertised products.

Table 3: Introducers of gou products	
Shree Ramachandrapura Math	43
Maa Gou Concern	01
Gou product vendors	04
Havyaka Friends	08
Havyaka Sabha programmes	15
Havyaka Mandala	01
Relatives	01
Medias	00
Source: Field Survey in Mangaluru Region	

Propagation by Gou Products Users of Havyakas and Corresponding Response: Many respondents made an attempt to introduce and propagate Maa gou products to others irrespective of community. 46 respondents propagandize and propagated gou products to others. Among them, 39 have got good response. 92 respondents have given the opinion that it needs propaganda. Few suggested to having own Maa gou product stall in many places. Many said that the gou product should be made available in common bazaars where many people go for their daily purchase of other products.

Gou Products and Response from Users about the Product: Commonly used 25 Gou Ganga products name was asked to the respondents. Users' details of 20 Gou Ganga products were showed in Table-4. 20 used Mosquito coil, 44 used Nivedana, 38 used Nirmalaganga, 38 used Danthamanjana, 48 used Gou Arka, 54 used Gou clean - Phenyl, 12 used Shamana Thaila, 12 used Panchagavya Ghrutha, 21 used Sucharana, 10 used Netrasaara, 4 used Sukhesha, 10 used Surabhi Dhoop, 3 used Himagiri Thaila, 20 used Triguna Vibhoothi, 6 used Tulasisara, 2 used Naasa Sanjeevini, 5 used Haridrasara, 1 used Naari sanjeevini, 6 used Abhyanga Thaila, 3 used Gomayadi Thaila, 2 used Bilvasara, 1 used Vaatsalya, 10 used Keetaniyantraka, 4 used Goukhanda and 1 used Tvachamrutha. All users liked these products and appreciated its use. In a survey, among all gou products, Gou clean – Phenyl, Gou Arka, Nivedana, Danthamanjana, Nirmalaganga, Mosquito coil are the leading demanded gou products. Numbers of users are more in these products.

Table 4: Commonly used Gou- Ganga products	No. of Users
Mosquito coil	20
Nivedana	44
Nirmalaganga	38
Danthamanjana (tooth powder)	38
Gou Arka	48
Gou clean - Phenyl	54
Shamanathaila	12
Netrasaara	10
Sukhesha	04
Surabhi Dhoop	10
Himagiri thaila	03
Triguna Vibhoothi	20
Tulasisara	06
Naasa Sanjeevini	02
Abhyanga thaila	06
Gomayadi thaila	03
Bilvasara	02
Keetaniyantraka	10
Goukhanda	04
Tvachamrutha	01
Source: Field Survey in Mangaluru Region	

Most Impressed Gou Products: Majority of respondents was interested and liked the Maa- gou products. All products are non chemical and organic based. Statistics of such products are shown in the table-5. Users of Maa- gou products commented in the following ways: 42 respondents said that Gou clean – Phenyl is the best organic product to repel housefly and ants; Tulasisara is good for cold, cough and asthma; Haridrasara for allergies and skin diseases, 35 respondents commented that Nivedana as headache balm is also useful in sprain and back pain; 18 respondents were happy to say that Danthamanjana keeps away Tooth ache, bleeding and bad odour. Gou Arka helps in immunity development as stated by 18 users. 16 users said that Nirmalaganga – bath scrubber is a best preventor of sunburn; 7 respondents stated that Shamanathaila is the best oil for backache and sprain and gives quick relief. 6 respondents said that sucharana is the best cracks heal balm; 4 commented that Mosquito coil is the best repellent of all insects including mosquitoes. All respondents were impressed by its medicinal use.

	Table 5: Impressed Products	User-Commenters
1	Mosquito coil	4
2	Nivedana	35
3	Nirmalaganga	16
4	Danthamanjana	18
5	Gou Arka	18
6	Gou clean - Phenyl	42
7	Shamanathaila	7
8	Sucharana	6
9	Tulasisara	2
10	Haridrasara	2
Source: Field Survey in Mangaluru Region		

Findings:

- ✓ 73 families have used gou products. Majority of them were using it for 1 to 10 years.
- ✓ Majority of respondents found the medicinal values in gou products, which does not have side effects.
- ✓ Shree Ramachandrapura Math and Shree Guruji popularized these gou products to 43 families among the 73 users.
- ✓ 46 respondents propagandize and propagated gou products to others. 39 have got good response too.
- ✓ Nivedana, Danthamanjana (tooth powder), Gou Arka, Gou clean – Phenyl, Mosquito coil were the leading demanded gou products.
- ✓ Majority of respondents were interested and liked the Maa- Gou products as they are non chemical and organic based.

Suggestions: More efforts are needed to make known to all about the gou products. A few suggestions are made accordingly.

- ✓ Mouth to mouth publicity and home to home campaign is needed by users.
- ✓ Users' feedback about each product is to be taken.
- ✓ Articles related to gou products are to be published in newspapers along with user customer opinion.
- ✓ Gou product user benefits are to be uploaded in whatsapp by users.
- ✓ Pamphlets related to gou products with its use are to be distributed to each and every family with user opinion.
- ✓ Easy availability of the products along with other ayurvedic and desi products will definitely increase the publicity of gou products.
- ✓ Success stories of users of gou products are to be published in diary and calendars.
- ✓ Present gou products to others as a gift item.

Conclusion:

Environment friendly products are very rare. Agriculture, horticulture and pharmaceutical joint development is possible with Desi cows. Hitherto called waste of its urine and cow dung is of high medicinal values which are known to others by the manufactures of gou products. Maa gou is one of such great concerns which produces many gou products and is used by many havvaka families. Still more publicity and propogation is needed. Let all show passion and tend towards Gou and Gou products.

References:

1. Primary data through interview through questionnaire.
2. Secondary source from gou yatra mahamangala at Mangaluru held in January 2017.
3. Secondary source from www.gouganga.com